

SUBCOMPONENT TESTING FOR ROTOR BLADES OF WIND TURBINES

A.M. van Wingerde^{1*}, F. Sayer¹, A.E. Antoniou¹, F. Bürkner¹, E. Putnam¹

¹Competence Center Rotor Blade, Fraunhofer IWES, Bremerhaven, Germany

* Corresponding author (arno.van.wingerde@iwes.fraunhofer.de)

Keywords: *wind turbine, rotor blade, subcomponent, test, certification*

1 Introduction

The current certification process for rotor blades of wind turbines is essentially based upon a number of coupon tests to establish the material properties, followed by a full scale blade test to check the design of the blade. Hardly anything is tested on the intermediate subcomponent level, except for the root connections, where subcomponent tests are carried out. This situation contrasts starkly to other industries where tests at the intermediate level are far more commonly used to verify the design assumptions and optimize structural details.

Not only does the current procedure in principle require a full scale blade test when even a single material or structural detail is exchanged, but the available worldwide test capacity, especially for larger blades, is insufficient to carry out all required tests, causing major delays in blade development.

Another problem with the current approach is the lack of statistical data for the blades, since typically only one blade is tested. Furthermore, it can safely be assumed that the lack of standards for certification based on subcomponent test is a serious impediment to the development of new rotor blades: full scale blade tests are hardly suitable for what-if scenarios, where various solutions for a structural problem are compared on an experimental basis.

2 Full scale blade testing according to 1 IEC 61400-23 [1]

The work on 61400-23 was first published as a technical specification in 2001. Work has continued since then, resulting in a standard which is currently being voted on by the member states. A major difference between this upcoming IEC standard and the GL standard is the requirement of a dynamic test of the blade. From a technical point of view this makes perfect sense: many manufacturing errors

cause failure during fatigue tests – after the static tests have been successfully concluded.

2.1 purpose of the IEC 61400-23 blade test

A full-scale blade test is current method of proving experimentally that a design meets the required standard. In the IEC61400-23 the purpose of a blade test is outlined as follows:

“The fundamental purpose of a wind turbine blade test is to demonstrate to a reasonable level of certainty that a blade type, when manufactured according to a certain set of specifications, has the prescribed reliability with reference to specific limit states, or, more precisely, to verify that the specified limit states are not reached and the blades therefore possess the load carrying capability and service life provided for in the design.

Additionally, tests determining blade properties have to be performed in order to validate some vital design assumptions used as inputs for the design load calculations. It has to be pointed out that the required blade property tests do not cover all design assumptions.

Normally, the full-scale tests dealt with in this standard are tests on a limited number of samples; only one or two blades of a given design are tested, so no statistical distribution of production blade load carrying capability can be obtained. Although the tests do give information valid for the blade type, they cannot replace either a rigorous design process or the quality system for series blade production. Furthermore, the tests described in this standard are not intended to be used for the testing of mechanism function nor to establish basic material strength or fatigue design data for blades and/or components.”

2.2 limitations of the IEC 61400-23 blade test

It is important to mention what is inherently not tested:

- Validity of design loads
- Environmental conditions
- Scatter in results
- Changes in production or design

It is especially important to notice that most failures occurring during certification testing are due to manufacturing defects, so the necessary omission of any testing of subsequently produced blades makes a stringent quality control system vital to the integrity of the produced blades. Given the frequent occurrence of failures during testing and the rather high variation in the quality of the produced blades, the industry has a major challenge ahead to produce more reliable blades, without a major cost increase. Particularly for offshore applications, where the rental of a vessel can be some €200,000 per day, and requiring a few days in case of adverse weather conditions. These costs, added to the loss caused by months of standstill, for turbines not accessible all year round, render the costs of manufacturing defects in blades unacceptable.

2.3 overview of the IEC 61400-23 blade test

Although IEC allows for other options, a typical blade test contains the following steps:

1. Determination of the dead weight, and center of gravity of the blade
2. Installation of a number of strain gauges on the blade, sometimes also on the bolts that connect the blade to the pitch bearing or adaptor plate.
3. Measurement of the natural frequencies of the blade
4. A static blade test, typically in 4 directions at 90° (flapmin, flapmax, lead-lagmin, lead-lagmax), see Figure 1.
5. Fatigue tests in 2 directions, (flap- and lead-lag-wise), see Figure 2.
6. A static test as in step 4

2.4 Weight and center of gravity

To verify that the design and manufacture together produce a blade with the specified design weight and manufacture upon arriving at the testing facility the blade is weighed and its center of gravity is

determined. The blade may or may not be weighed with the root bolts installed.

2.5 Installation of sensors

The installation of sensors, mostly strain gauges, occurs right after weighing the blade so that the gauges can be utilized throughout the testing program. Both uni-axial gauges and rosettes are utilized to measure the various strain deformations. At several cross sections along the length of the blade a minimum of 4 gauges are installed around the section on the spar caps on the high and low pressure sides, on the leading edge, and on the trailing edge to measure the longitudinal strain responses in the static and fatigue testing. The rosettes are typically installed on the shear web inside the blade to monitor the shear in the biax laminates. Additional uniaxial gauges may be installed on a few root bolts to monitor the tension and bending that results in the tightening of the bolts and during the static testing.

2.6 Measurement of natural frequencies

The measurement of the natural frequencies of the blade provides the first chance for the designer and manufacturer to experimentally verify the stiffness and mass distribution. A comparison with the calculated natural frequencies can quickly reveal flaws in design assumptions or deviations from the design during the manufacturing stages.

The main objective of the testing is to determine the first few natural frequencies and their corresponding modes, in the flap and lead-lag directions. The testing and analysis can be expanded to include determination of the modal damping. Various methods exist to determine the natural frequencies and their mode shapes, which include impact excitation, using a fast Fourier transform (FFT) and frequency response function (FRF), respectively. In addition to the use of impact excitation, is the ability to shake the blade into a specific mode shape either by hand or with a mass exciter.

A distributed network of instrumentation along the length of the blade must be employed to measure the excited responses. Typical instrumentation are multi-axis accelerometers and/or strain gauges.

Determining the natural frequencies is typically conducted at the beginning and end of the testing program, after the post-fatigue static test. Conducting the test at the beginning and end of the

program allows for an easy evaluation of accumulated damages and their effect on the stiffness and thus the frequency response of the blade. Additional natural frequency tests might be conducted after specific stages of the testing, i.e. after the fatigue testing, to determine the effect of one specific test on any changes in the natural frequency.

2.7 Static blade test

The static blade test applies the most critical loads along the length of the blade to verify (1) that these loads can be resisted and (2) that the strains and deflections match the predicted values from the calculations. Setup of a static test consists of cantilevering the blade from a large and rigid support block and fixing loading frames to the blade, as shown in Figure 1. IWES uses the load frames and pulling concept, downward vertical that is shown in Figure 1; however, other concepts are also widely used.

Additional instrumentation to the strain gauges used during a static test include: displacement measurements, to measure the main pulling axis deflection, often through the use of draw wire sensors; load cells, to measure the applied forces; and possibly angle sensors, to measure the change in slope at various points on the blade. For most static tests IWES employs the use of 4 to 6 load application points and corresponding displacement measurement points, as well as at the tip.

As previously stated, a static test is often conducted for 4 directions, where each angle is a 90° rotation from the other, and the goal is to load the main structural elements in the flap and lead-lag directions. For the flap tests this means the load carrying spars on the high and low pressure sides. For the lead-lag tests this means the trailing and leading edges.

The four directions and the axes of the blade to which the loading corresponds are:

1. flap_{min} = high pressure side under compression
2. flap_{max} = low pressure side under compression
3. lead-lag_{min} = trailing edge under compression
4. lead-lag_{max} = leading edge under compression

Loading for a static test is conducted quasi-statically with the load applied in a few load steps up to the 100% required test load. At each of these load steps the experimental deflections and strains can be verified against the expected and a determination

can be made on whether to advance the test further. At 100% the load is held for a minimum of 10 sec to allow for the load to settle before the load is released back to zero.

2.8 Fatigue blade tests

To verify the designed lifetime, dynamic fatigue testing is conducted on the blade. As with the static testing, the loading is directed to load the structural elements in the flap and lead-lag directions. Again, the blade is cantilevered from a large and rigid support block and at least one load frame is mounted on the blade to attach an exciter to the blade, as is shown in Figure 2. IWES employs the use of an externally mounted hydraulic cylinder as an exciter with either the cylinder pushrod or a pushrod coupled to the movement of the cylinder attached to the load frame. Figure 2 illustrates the setup of a fatigue test for a bi-axial fatigue test; therefore, both the flap and lead-lag direction load structures are shown. The flap direction loading, to excite the blade vertically, is accomplished through the cylinder which is attached directly to the load frame. The lead-lag direction loading, to excite the blade horizontally, is accomplished by the pushrod attached to the load frame, which is coupled to the movement of the cylinder through the use of a bell crank. Additional load frames may be added to the blade for the fatigue test to adjust the bending moment distribution to more closely match the specified test bending moment.

Additional instrumentation to the strain gauges already installed on the blade include: accelerometers; to track the dynamic movement; load cells, on the cylinder pushrod or coupled pushrod; and displacement measurement of the cylinder pushrod.

The industry standard is not the bi-axial fatigue testing as shown, but is uni-axial testing, in flap or lead-lag direction. Both tests will be conducted; one after the other, but the order of the two is not significant. The loading cycles for the flap and lead-lag tests typically varies between 1 and 5 million cycles, which depends on the load amplitude that is applied to the blade.

Tuning of the fatigue tests is done to reach the required bending moment along the length of the blade. IWES conducts a static bending moment calibration in both the flap and lead-lag directions to establish the correlation of strain and bending

moment at a specific point in the blade. The strain from the calibration is a measured value and the bending moment is computed based upon the measured force in the calibration and the radius of application of the force. With these calibration parameters, the bending moment when the blade is moved dynamically is calculated from the actual strains and the calibration parameters. Throughout the fatigue test program, a few re-tunings are conducted to ensure that as the blade accumulates damages the testing parameters are still achieving the required loadings.

In addition to the re-tunings throughout the fatigue testing program, inspections are typically conducted at regular intervals to check for any damages that might have been caused due to the testing. The standard inspections are visual inspections of the blade on the inside and outside. Inspection routines for the flap direction testing would concentrate on the spar caps on the high and low pressure sides and for the lead-lag direction on the leading and trailing edges. Any damages found are noted and then closely monitored for the rest of the testing to track their progression.

2.9 Post-fatigue static tests

At the end of the testing of the rotor blade an additional static test is conducted to verify that the blade can still withstand the most critical load cases even near the end of its useful life-span. Therefore, another full round of static tests, all four directions, is completed on the blade prior to the end of the testing program.

3 Conclusions on the full-scale blade test

A number of advantages and disadvantages are inherent to the full-scale blade test and will be discussed here as a starting point for the alternatives.

3.1 Advantages of the full-scale blade test

A full scale blade test is essentially a rather efficient way to test a blade: the support structure can be bolted to the blade root using the existing blade to turbine connection, which is both convenient and realistic.

The very length of blade allows for large bending moments to be achieved with relatively modest applied forces, thus simplifying the load introduction and omitting overly large shear forces in the blade. The blade itself is loaded in operation only by its

dead weight and the wind forces, both distributed loads, and is ill suited to take concentrated forces. Indeed the number of load frames seen in Figure 1 is not only aimed at producing the best approximation of the bending moment in the blade, but rather at limiting the concentrated forces and maximum shear loads in the blade.

Also, with one test series as outlined in Chapter 2, static-dynamic-static, a large part of the blade structure is tested and the test has a fairly direct relation to the loads the blade encounters in practice with relatively simple boundary conditions to observe. The major violation of the boundary conditions is caused by the load frames which apply concentrated loads, rather than distributed loads and locally support the blade against instabilities. Therefore the IEC considers an area of 0.75 times the blade width from both sides of each load frame to be invalid.

3.2 Testing time related problems with full-scale blade test

The requirement for fatigue tests of the rotor blade, while sensible from a technical point of view, increases the testing time for rotor blades. Most blades are tested at their natural frequency, in order to save on energy and reach a proper bending moment distribution over the length of the blade. For larger blades, this means that the testing time increases because of the lower natural frequency, often as low as 0.4 Hz for the first flap natural frequency. At this frequency, 1 million cycles takes 29 days. While tests are frequently interrupted, due to inspections or system shut-downs, the actual testing time is significantly larger.

For large blades, the dead weight of the blades becomes a dominant load case, one that cannot be countered by adding extra material, forcing the designer to maximize the utilization of the blade material. Together with the rather severe load factors on the fatigue load, this causes the fatigue load on the blade to be at the edge of the technical possibilities, causing many designers to increase the number of cycles in order to be able to reduce the fatigue loads. This effect often results in blade tests with for instance 5 million cycles, which would require 5 months full-time testing for just the flap direction, or as much as one year for a complete blade test. During this time the tremendous

investments in the blade design, the form, the prototyping, etc. is put on hold, to await the certification test. For this reason, most manufacturers produce 4 prototype blades, 1 for the certification test in the lab, and the next 3 go onto a prototype turbine for the next step in the certification process, directly after the first series of static tests have been carried out.

However, since more errors are exposed during fatigue testing than during static testing, it is hard to argue against the necessity of fatigue testing. The increasing testing time, coupled with a lack of testing facilities worldwide for larger blades, causes a major delay in blade testing, in effect hampering the industry as a whole. Thus, it becomes imperative to look for alternatives to a full-scale test method.

3.3 Full-scale blade test as obstacle for innovation

The lack of testing facilities and the enormous cost and time involved in the certification test of the blade are but one aspect of the stifling influence of the required full-scale blade test. Equally bad, perhaps worse, is that the slightest change in design or manufacturing process or materials used would in principle require a whole new blade test... hardly inviting minor improvements in either the design or production of the blades. Also, the manufacturers have no simple path to carry out tests to prove the various design options experimentally and cannot build a catalogue of details of which the structural properties, both static and fatigue, are known and accepted by the certification bodies. Unlike most other industries, where tests of smaller parts are quite customary, many manufacturers stick to tested and true blade designs within the company, since the risks involved are tremendous.

4 Current status of the component tests

Relatively few tests subcomponent test are widely used in the rotor blade development on a systematic basis, although the upcoming IEC standard allows for this [3], see also Figure 5.

4.1 Existing subcomponent tests

The single well-known test carried out today is on root laminate, such as the one shown in Figure 3, with typically three T-bolts or inserts tested, whereby the middle connection is the one aimed for since the edge effects are smaller. This test is used to demonstrate the load carrying capacity of the root

connection where often high loads need to be transferred by relatively little material under complex load conditions.

Another test, shown in Figure 4, has been developed by Fraunhofer IWES and Henkel [2] and is now proposed as a standard. It consists of an I-beam where the web and flanges are bonded with the bonding paste to be evaluated. This test represents a more elaborate, but far more realistic alternative to the lap-shear tests mentioned in, for instance, the GL standard.

4.2 Ad-hoc subcomponent tests

Other subcomponent tests are carried out on an ad-hoc basis, where the test specimen is designed to model the structural detail considered. Acceptance by the certification body should be cleared in advance, since no defined standards exist. As publicly available data is lacking, a comparison between various solutions and materials requires a relatively large effort, since all combinations have to be tested for each interested manufacturer separately and interpretation of the results is open for debate.

An example of such tests is the use of beams for testing the shear behavior of core materials, or the effect of ply-drops, modeled in the webs, or the trailing edge of a blade, tested in axial direction with a suitable eccentricity.

5 Testing of blade sections

Instead of testing the blade in one piece, the blade could also be cut at one or more radii and tested as such. The advantage is that the testing frequency can be increased significantly, and smaller lab space is needed to test large blades. Producing 2 blades would allow for an overlap between inner- and outer-board parts, thus the whole blade length could be tested. A major problem with this alternative is the introduction of the load for the inner-board part: applying the appropriate bending moment, without excessive shear forces. Similarly, the clamping of the outboard part can be problematic as well.

Using the calculation sheets used at Fraunhofer IWES for establishing blade test offers, and ignoring the extra effort needed for setting up the outboard test the results of a full scale blade test in one part and that of a blade segment at 50% of its radius can be compared, in order to see whether the gains in testing time may offset the increase in testing costs.

Two examples are considered: a blade of 40 m length and a blade of 80m length.

5.1 Example 1, a typical 40 m blade

A blade of 40 m length is tested for 4 static loads, followed by 1 million cycles in flap-wise direction, 1.5 million cycles in lead-lag-wise direction, and concluded by another 4 static tests. 3 static frames are assumed, 80 strain gauges, 20 strain gauges rosettes and 24 strain gauges to measure the elongation and bending in the bolts between the blade and the pitch bearing. The main results are presented in Table 1. The frequencies exceeding 2 Hz are shaded, because it is deemed impractical to test at these frequencies. The main conclusion is that for a 50% increase in costs, the testing time has been decreased from 6 to 5 months, hardly an interesting trade-off even if the additional effort of setting up the outboard testing are ignored.

5.2 Example 2, a typical 80 m blade

A blade of 80 m length is tested for 4 static loads, followed by 3 million cycles in flap-wise direction, 3 million cycles in lead-lag-wise direction, and concluded by another 4 static tests. 6 static frames are assumed, 160 strain gauges, 40 strain gauges rosettes and 24 strain gauges to measure the elongation and bending in the bolts between the blade and the pitch bearing.

The differences in cycles, and strain gauges, with the 40 m long blade, though by no means the same for all customers, is considered indicative for the difference in testing set-up between small and large blades as observed at our institute.

The main results are presented in Table 2. The main conclusion is that for a 15% increase in testing costs, plus additional effort for setting up the outboard test, the testing time has been decreased from 13 to slightly less than 9 months. In contrast to the example, the blade would typically be cut at 50 m, instead of 40 m radius, so the inboard and outboard test would take about the same amount of time. Given the major investments made by the manufacturer, cutting the blade could present a viable alternative in this case.

6 Testing of blade components: outlook

6.1 Cutting a blade into components

Cutting a blade into sections is relatively straightforward, and clamping of sections is widely practiced for load introduction of full blade tests. On the other hand, cutting components out of a blade is a lot harder to define. Components to be taken out of a blade are shown in Figure 6.

6.2 Technical problems associated with component testing

However, the hardest technical problem for these component tests is assuring realistic boundary conditions while at the same time taking care that the specimens fail at the testing area, rather than near the load introduction or supports. For instance for the trailing edge test, shown in Figure 7, the blade component would experience an axial load, with a bending moment, so an eccentric loading condition. Worse, the trailing edge is supported at the longitudinal edges of the test specimen by the adjacent blade parts, a condition that is omitted in the setup shown. When it can be expected that leaving out this support is generally conservative, it would be acceptable, but it cannot be proven without careful numerical modeling that the effect would not be detrimental, for instance due to the “breathing” effects of the blade under bending, leading to a situation which would pry open the trailing edge and which could be detrimental. On the other hand, all too conservative results would not benefit the manufacturer, since the results would not lead to more economical blade designs. The efficiency of the full blade test in terms of load introduction and material tested is hard to top.

6.3 Acceptance problems associated with component testing

The non-technical issues are just as major: without standards, the certification bodies may not accept the test results in lieu of a complete blade test, whereas the lack of standards and comparison materials limits the use for blade development. Within the IEC committees, some doubt remains to include tests for which no standard exists – a chicken-and-egg problem.

A major international cooperation between research centers, certification bodies, manufacturers and material suppliers is necessary to develop internationally accepted standards. Meanwhile, the parallel development of substandard tests like the root tests and Henkel beams shows that there

certainly is a major interest in the development of component testing.

This way, a catalog of standardized subcomponent tests can be developed and accepted by the certification bodies. The manufacturer has become the option of not just testing materials before manufacturing a whole blade and having that tested, but can prove to the certification body that the various structures fulfill their intended purpose, so the development of new rotor blade concept can be speeded up considerably and flexibility of small changes can be increased .

Fig. 1. Static blade test, about 5 m tip displacement

Fig. 2. Dynamic bi-axial blade test

Fig.3. A typical root connection test.

Fig.4. "Henkel beam" used for testing bonding paste.

Fig. 5. Testing hierarchy according to IEC 61400-5 [3]

Fig. 6. Blade Components

Fig. 7. Leading edge test

Table 1, a 40 m blade test

Blade length	40 m	40 m	40 m
		0-20	20-40m
Weight [ton]	5.8	4.4	1.4
Flap 1. freq [Hz]	0.9	3.4	1.4
Lead-lag 1. freq [Hz]	1.6	5.2	3.2
Time [months]	6.0	5.2	5.0
Test costs [k€]	340	280	290¹
Blade costs [k€]	150		150²
Total [k€]	490		720

Table 2, an 80 m blade test

Blade length	80 m	80 m	80 m
		0-40	40-80m
Weight [ton]	33.0	25.0	8.0
Flat 1. freq [Hz]	0.5	1.9	0.8
Lead-lag 1. freq [Hz]	0.8	2.6	1.6
Time [months]	13.0	7.6	9.3
Test costs [k€]	1050	610	720¹
Blade costs [k€]	800		800²
Total [k€]	1850		2130

¹ Excl. additional costs for clamping outer blade half

² For two blades used, in order to be able to test the overlapping part, these costs double

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